

Polarographic Study of Cd(II)-Acetylacetonate System

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BRANICA^{1,2} and co-workers have undertaken polarographic investigations on acetylacetonate complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II). The present study deals with the polarography of Cd(II)-acetylacetonate system.

Experimental

Solutions of CdCl₂, NaNO₃ were prepared from reagent grade chemicals in conductivity water. Acetylacetonate was of E. Merck G. R. grade and its aqueous solution was used as ligand. The concentration of Cd(II) in each case was kept at 1×10⁻³ M. The concentration of acetylacetonate ion was calculated from the pH of the solution and pK value³⁻⁵ of acetylacetonate (pK=8.95).

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) with polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL-50) was used. All the measurements were recorded at 30 ± 0.1°. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution to remove the dissolved oxygen. Saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E.) was used as reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1M NaNO₃, open circuit): m=1.673 mg/sec, t=4.04 sec, m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=1.778 mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}, h_{o,r,r}=63.01 cm. The number of electrons(n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon⁶. This gave the value of n=2 at pH 7.

The thermodynamic functions (ΔG, ΔH and ΔS) have been evaluated using relevant equations⁷.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of the solutions containing 1×10⁻³ M Cd(II) and 0.1 M acetylacetonate were taken at different pH values. It was observed that the negative shift in E_{1/2} was maximum at pH 7 and hence this value was chosen for studying the complex formation between Cd(II) and acetylacetonate. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 0.01 to 0.1 M. In each case a single well-defined wave appeared. The plots of i_a vs h_{o,r,r}^{1/2} were found to be linear and passing through the origin thereby indicating that the reduction is diffusion-controlled. The plots of log i/i_a - i vs E_{a.e.} were found to be linear with slope of the order of 31 ± 2 mV. This shows that the reduction is reversible. The plot of E_{1/2} against -log C_o is a straight line. This suggests that Cd(II) forms a single complex with the ligand. The composition and stability constants have been determined by Lingane's⁸ method.

The value of co-ordination number, p, comes out to be 1. The composition of the complex is, therefore,

[Cd(Acac)]⁺. The value of stability-constant has been determined at three different temperatures (20°, 30° and 40°).

The values of stability constant (β) and the thermodynamic functions (ΔG, ΔH and ΔS) have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF LOG β AND ΔG, ΔH AND ΔS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR Cd(II)-ACETYLACETONATE SYSTEM
μ=0.1 (NaNO₃)

Temp. °C	log β	Δ H Kcal mole ⁻¹	Δ G Kcal mole ⁻¹	Δ S cal degree ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
20	4.28	-11.897	-5.74	-0.020
30	3.99	-11.897	-5.44	-0.021
40	3.69	-11.897	-5.12	-0.022

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Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species :
Part VIII. *Lumnitzera racemosa*

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A thorough investigation for secondary metabolites of Sundarban mangroves have been undertaken for chemotaxonomic consideration¹⁻⁶. In this present communication triterpenoid constituents of *Lumnitzera racemosa* (Fam. Combrataceae) from two different latitude viz. Kakinada (Lat 20° NH) and Sundarban (Lat. 16° NH) are described to determine the effect of insolation upon taxonomic markers.